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Submitted by Thomas Exner (EwC and 7P9), Martin Himly (PLUS), Beatriz Alfaro Serrano (BNN), Egon Willighagen (UM), Iseult Lynch (UoB)

Revised by Albert Duschl (PLUS) and Vladimir Lobaskin (UCD)

Approved by Iseult Lynch (UoB)

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Summary

This deliverable continues with reporting on the community-building and dissemination activities organized and performed by the NanoCommons consortium and builds on previous deliverables, especially D2.2 “1st set of Stakeholder Workshops and Report on Stakeholder feedback on the usability of NanoCommons portal and tools” (M20, August 2019), D2.5 “2nd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop with Transnational Access (TA) calls and demonstrations” (M27, March 2020) and D8.1 Training Needs Specification and Proposed Solutions. However, the focus of this deliverable is different to the previous ones. Instead of listing the events and the presentations given by the NanoCommons consortium, the events are evaluated with respect to the stakeholder categories reached (research projects, networks and clusters including industry-academic partnerships, regulators, industry, early-stage researchers, etc.) and identifies follow-up interactions and ongoing collaborations that will be part of the overall impact achieved by NanoCommons.

It is clear that tangible outcomes from events can only be expected sometime after the event has concluded and, thus, we also revisit earlier events, already reported in D2.5, with respect to TA applications and collaborative work started as a result of contacts made during the events at which NanoCommons partners specific tools and services and/or the NanoCommons project and the opportunities for TA were presented. This is complemented by reporting on interactions started with important projects or clusters of projects (safe by design, governance, materials modelling) and initiatives representing neighbouring, partly overlapping communities (toxicology & life sciences, pilot lines, virtual materials marketplace, data management) and how this has resulted in increased access to relevant stakeholders. We also provide an uptake on specific support offered to the EU NanoSafety Cluster and its member projects especially with respect to training and coordination and knowledge exchange in project clusters funded under a specific EU call. Finally, engagement with organisations such as the OECD, EUON and the InChi Trust are highlighted, as exemplary stakeholders who will be key partners in delivering on NanoCommons impact and enduring legacy.

Introduction

NanoCommons has the objective to deliver a sustainable and openly accessible nanosafety framework (knowledge infrastructure consisting of a knowledge base with rich information on methods, protocols and data as well as integrated computational tools, supported by expert advice, data interpretation and training) to support and strengthen the nanosafety community by bringing together scientists from different fields of nanosafety research bridging the gap towards industry and regulatory stakeholders to collectively move forward the field. Besides the development of the computational infrastructure, this goal can only be reached by outstandingly strong community and dissemination efforts. To highlight the importance of these aspects already in the description of action, NanoCommons established two, strongly interlinked networking activities WP, WP2 Community Building and WP9 Dissemination & Case studies, instead of the common dissemination WP in many other projects. The well organised interactions and mutual benefits of the two WPs but also the delay of and cancellation of conferences and workshops due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the delivery dates of the deliverable reports were adapted to more equally spread over the complete period of the time and minimise double reporting by reporting jointed efforts in multiple reports. Therefore, this deliverable on “Workshops with different stakeholders” delivered in M38 of the project can be seen as the direct sequel of the deliverables of WP2 and especially Deliverable D2.2 “1st set of Stakeholder Workshops and Report on Stakeholder feedback on the usability of NanoCommons portal and tools” (M20, August 2019) and D2.5 “2nd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop with TA calls and demonstrations” (M27, March 2020) and will be followed up by D2.7 “3rd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, social web activities, stakeholder workshop with TA calls/ demonstrations” (delivery date: M44, August 2021) and finally D8.3 “Final Report on Training Activities and analysis of stakeholder groups reached” (deliverable date: M54, June 2020).

This report describes the community-building and dissemination activities organized and performed by the NanoCommons consortium during the time following the D2.5 report. However, this report switches focus from listing the activities and presenting short summaries of their content to: (1) analysis of the impact these dissemination activities had and continue to have, (2) presentation of the work done in the NanoCommons project and especially the TA offerings and, (3) highlighting the uptake of the NanoCommons solutions by the community and different stakeholder groups.

We have structured the report into three main sections. The first section describes the identification of strategic collaborators to mutually facilitate the access and open new dissemination routes to reach major stakeholders. These are either established institutions within the nanosafety community or in neighboring communities with interest in nanosafety or have interest in reusing the solutions in their domain. The second section concentrates on the EU NanoSafety Cluster (NSC) and specific project groups within the cluster as major stakeholders. The final section reports on the stakeholder outreach undertaken during conferences and workshops NanoCommons organised and/or participated in. It also references the first two sections with respect to strategic collaborators involved in these meetings as invited presenters or as participants as well as stakeholders from the EU NSC reached.

Interactions with strategic collaborators to increase stakeholder access to NanoCommons outputs

We define *strategic collaborators* as multipliers which could open access to more stakeholders and lead to more customers and users of the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure by promotion and endorsement in the communities they represent. Within this section, we highlight why they are considered as key collaborators, how they can link NanoCommons to other communities and stakeholders, which additional channels for outreach could be established by these interactions and which stakeholder groups were added by these interactions.

Please, note, that these strategic collaborations are also an essential element of the sustainability efforts of the project, which is described in Deliverable D10.4 *First Testing and Evaluation Results of NanoCommons Sustainability Plan*.

EU NanoSafety Cluster (NSC)

The [EU NanoSafety Cluster \(NSC\)](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/)¹ is a natural strategic collaborator for NanoCommons since it combines and organises all the EU funded nanosafety projects to support knowledge sharing and collaboration and, thus, represents a large portion of the European nanosafety community. Many NanoCommons partners were already strongly involved in structuring the NSC even before the start of NanoCommons but this has intensified during its runtime. Several NanoCommons project partners act as chairs of different NSC working groups (WG), in specific, the [WG F on Data](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wgf/)² (Co-Chaired by partners UM and 7P9), the [WG A on Education, Training and Communication](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wga/)³ (Chaired by partner PLUS), the [WG C on Exposure & Hazard Assessment](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wgc/)⁴ (Chaired by partner UKCEH and co-chaired by partner LEITAT), [Working Group D on Models & Tools for Risk Assessment](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wgd/) (Co-Chaired by partner NovaM) and [WG G on Regulations & Risk Governance](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wgg/)⁵ (UoB and NovaM are members of the core team). They also are members of the [NSC's coordination team](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/coordination-team/)⁶ (UoB and BNN), initiating and providing leadership for the [NSC/NanoCommons Task Force on Ontologies](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/task-forces/tf-ontology-inventory/)⁷ (lead by partners 7P9 and UoB) and build the team of the [NSC's secretariat](https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/secretariat/)⁸ (UoB). As such, the community-building character of the NanoCommons project can be effectively transported into other projects and beyond. Being able to present the newest developments in these as well as the other working groups (e.g., WG G on Governance) gives visibility to the NanoCommons services and easy access to the stakeholders from other projects participating in the meetings and indirectly to all partners of the NSC projects and all

¹ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/>

² <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wgf/>

³ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wga/>

⁴ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wgc/>

⁵ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wgg/>

⁶ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/coordination-team/>

⁷ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/task-forces/tf-ontology-inventory/>

⁸ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/secretariat/>

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NSC members. Additionally, by securing prominent slots in conferences and workshops organised by the NSC and international activities partnering with the NSC like the U.S.-EU communities of research (CoRs), EU-Asia collaboration and the US Nano Working Group, the NSC supported NanoCommons in reaching stakeholders in the international arena from academia, industry and regulatory agencies. Examples of this are the NanoSAFE conference in November 2020 co-organised by the NSC and the keynote presentation at the virtual meeting of the U.S-EU CoRs (see below).

ELIXIR

ELIXIR unites Europe's leading life science organisations in managing and safeguarding the increasing volume of biological data. As such, it is the logical strategic collaborator to reach out to neighbouring communities in the life sciences and to align approaches and tools. The toxicology and nanosafety communities depend on ELIXIR services on many levels from data management for omics experiments, information resources on biomolecules to ontology tools and listings for tools, to (access to) models and training materials. To strengthen the interactions and interlinking of NanoCommons and ELIXIR, work concentrated on two aspects:

- 1) Establishing an ELIXIR Toxicology Community: ELIXIR Communities are a mechanism to formalise the collaboration between experts across Europe for developing standards, services and training within specific life science domains linked to the ELIXIR infrastructure. Such Communities can provide more direct feedback on the services offered by ELIXIR, can request new features or the inclusion of additional ELIXIR Core Resources and can even apply for community-led implementation studies funding work in a specific area to strengthen the ELIXIR portfolio. Led by NanoCommons and especially partner UM (part of ELIXIR-NL), an application to establish an ELIXIR Toxicology Community also representing the nanotoxicology and nanosafety community was filed in 2019 and approved. In March 2020, a workshop was organized in Amsterdam but due to the pandemic had to be cancelled at short notice. The meeting was subsequently held virtually in September, where community members collaboratively worked on the writing of an ELIXIR whitepaper, which is being prepared for submission to F1000Research. NanoCommons was one of the participating EU NSC projects.

The new community will focus on mutual benefit, an open and inclusive community, solving practical community problems. The goal is to develop a pragmatic approach that provides FAIR and Open solutions, allowing all toxicology and neighboring communities to benefit from these harmonized solutions. Open licensing and interfaces (ontologies, standards, formats) will encourage new solutions and collaborations, which will be accessible to any organisation and project within and beyond Europe. These goals overlap completely with the objectives of NanoCommons, and the community is an excellent opportunity to make ELIXIR aware of the needs of the nanosafety community and adapt the ELIXIR services to address these needs and to increase interoperability and build interfaces to NanoCommons services addressing needs which cannot be satisfied by ELIXIR resources.

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- 2) Exchange of training material and guidance documents: ELIXIR and NanoCommons work in many overlapping areas like metadata standards, ontology development and service listings to name just a few. Therefore, both infrastructures can profit from each other by exchanging information on developed concepts and approaches and experiences but also pitfalls during their practical implementation. One way to exchange such knowledge is by participating in each other's training and also having easy access to the developed training materials over the longer term. To partly automate these exchanges and in this way reach a larger stakeholder group, a team including Egon Willighagen from UM, Niall Beard from ELIXIR, and Oana Florean from EwC has used BioSchemas to create [a system](#)⁹ that automatically pulls toxicology-related training materials from the eNanoMapper project into [TeSS](#)¹⁰, the training portal of ELIXIR. This will be continued to provide all the NanoCommons-developed material to TeSS. Figure 1 shows the currently available content on TeSS provided by NanoCommons as a training content provider.

European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials (EUON)

The [European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials \(EUON\)](#)¹¹ operated by the European Chemicals Agency provides information about existing nanomaterials (NMs) on the EU market. Their mandate is to act as the repository for interesting reading about the safety, innovation, research and uses of NMs for policy makers in the area, consumers, industry representatives and green non-governmental organisations. EUON was established in response to calls for a European registry of nano-enabled products, akin to those established in France, Denmark and elsewhere¹², but has a broader focus to share information about NMs benefits and risks, including showcasing research from the extensive EU-funded nanosafety research projects and the pilot lines projects that are working on scale-up of NMs production. EUON is working together with the EU-funded projects to constantly add content to inform and guide their stakeholders, including offering “info cards” summarising the information available regarding uses on the market, hazards and other available information - see for example the EUON info card on [cerium dioxide](#)¹³ which despite being widely utilised and listed had limited information available as yet. Given that cerium dioxide was on the OECD sponsorship list, and is a JRC representative test material, was studied in the FP7 project NanoREG and several other projects, there is clearly significant data available in the public domain that has not yet been usefully integrated into EUON, in a manner that allows automated updating as new information becomes available, and which allows users to differentiate between research results and regulatory information (e.g. performed and reported in a highly standardised way).

⁹<https://www.dtls.nl/2018/07/19/toxicology-data-management-tutorials-automatically-collected-by-european-training-portal-tess/>

¹⁰<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

¹¹<https://euon.echa.europa.eu/>

¹²<https://euon.echa.europa.eu/national-reporting-schemes>

¹³<https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.013.774>

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Figure 1. Screenshot from the [ELIXIR-TeSS webspace¹⁴](https://tess.elixir-europe.org/content_providers/nanocommons) where NanoCommons is listed as a training content provider.

One important aspect is availability of data as well as nanoinformatics methods to, on the one hand, support industry to better evaluate the safeness of NMs and apply safe-by-design early in their development cycle and, on the other side, to avoid unnecessary testing and especially reduce animal testing by the reuse of data and promoting read-across and classification approaches. NanoCommons is becoming a central hub for harmonised and interoperable data and is integrating data from more and more projects. To make this interesting resource also available to EUON users, discussion and first steps have been started to use NanoCommons as the resource to provide experimental data including

¹⁴ https://tess.elixir-europe.org/content_providers/nanocommons

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detailed information on the underlying test methods and protocols. At the moment, the eNanoMapper database is loosely linked to EUON providing access to a limited amount of data. NanoCommons could substitute this since it also provides access to the eNanoMapper and associated databases via the database linking mechanism. Additionally, it could offer more direct usage of the data applying the nanoinformatics and risk assessment workflows developed in NanoCommons. Due to this collaboration, NanoCommons is becoming better known and gets access to the stakeholders of EUON especially industrial scientists, risk assessors and regulators and can, based on their feedback, optimise and validate the offers for regulatory usage.

A series of dedicated workshops with EUON have occurred during 2019 and 2020 to scope-out what implementation of NanoCommons KnowledgeBase into EUON would entail, which included presentations by the NanoCommons team on the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase, by EUON on the IUCLID6 database and how it is being utilized to capture data on nanoforms and sets of nanoforms, and the development of a TA application by EUON for dedicated developmental time to support the integration of the KnowledgeBase into EUON, including consideration of how NanoCommons data can feed into and build up the EUON “info cards” for specific NMs, as well as allowing 2-way exchange of data between NanoCommons and IUCLID6 to support modelling and data integration, whilst of course being compliant with data licensing and confidentiality issues. NanoCommons are also collaborating with EUON and the risk governance projects on development of a check-list and data quality criteria for information coming into EUON to ensure its fitness for purpose - further details are provided under the collaboration with the risk governance projects.

European Material Modelling Council (EMMC)

The EMMC was initially funded as an EU H2020 Coordination & Support Action between 2015-2018 and in 2019 the non-profit Association, EMMC ASBL, was created to ensure continuity, growth and sustainability of EMMC activities for all stakeholders including modellers, materials data scientists, software owners, translators and manufacturers in Europe. During the project, a series of roadmaps were elaborated that identified major obstacles to widening the use of materials modelling in European industry and proposed strategies to overcome them. Another major initiative, of relevance to NanoCommons, was the development of the [Modelling Data Elements \(MODA\)](#) templates as a means to harmonise the reporting of materials models (computational models) and a modelling workflow where model integration is required. However, the current version is very text-based which allows quite some variability and inconsistency, which prevents interoperability and findability of the description, so NanoCommons has been working to find ways to harmonise the form content even further including through ontological terms and utilisation of drop-down menus for standardised aspects such as software packages, programming languages, etc.

The EMMC considers the integration of materials modelling and digitalisation critical for more agile and sustainable product development, and a strong collaboration with NanoCommons could foster the inclusion of safe-by-design features at very early stages (see also the European Network for Pilot

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Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs below). A follow-on project to EMMC, developing a Virtual Marketplace for Materials ([VIMMP¹⁵](#)) hosted a series of webinars in which NanoCommons partner UCD participated, and the subsequent discussion confirmed two clear areas with strong needs for collaboration and harmonization: 1) NMs and simulation ontologies and 2) harmonisation and further standardisation of MODA reporting templates.

The EMMC developed an initial [European Materials Modelling Ontology framework¹⁶](#) based on current materials modelling and characterization knowledge. It is the top-level ontology of the [Virtual Materials Marketplace \(VIMMP\)](#) and reuses other ontologies like the Ontology for Simulation, Modelling, and Optimization (OSMO, described in Horsch et al., 2020) as the semiformal simulation workflow graph standard in the [MODA reporting standard¹⁷](#). However, nanosafety-related ontologies like the eNanoMapper ontology describing the nanoparticles are not included properly in EMMO. EMMC members have started to contribute to the EU NSC and NanoCommons ontology developments on definition of modelling and computational terms to ensure alignment with the EMMO. There are also first steps to integrate the EMMO into the NanoCommons sets of ontologies available directly from the ontology lookup services in the NanoCommons Knowledge Base.

The second, related area of collaboration is to promote the use of the MODA and the associated OSO (*Ontology for Simulation, Modelling, and Optimization*) ontology for documenting simulations both for NMs design and nanosafety. Web tools for automatic generation of MODA sheets using the existing OSO or other ontology terms via lookup services would highly reduce the effort to create these reports. A TA application is drafted building on approaches developed in ACEnano for protocols and integrated as one of the 4 options into the NanoCommons Protocols repository linked to the Knowledge Base (see also Deliverable report D3.2). The work on adding the further relevant terms to the OSO ontology will continue in UCD in collaboration with the VIMMP consortium.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

The OECD have been active in the assessment of NMs safety since the establishment of the Working Party on Manufactured Nanomaterials (WPMN) in 2006, whose goal was to promote international co-operation in human health and environmental safety aspects of manufactured NMs¹⁸. Its aim is to assist member countries in their efforts to assess the safety implications of NMs, a core aspect of which has been the revision and updating of the OECD test guidelines and Guidance documents to ensure their relevance for NMs safety testing, given particulate nature and dynamic nature of NMs.

In 2018 the WPMN launched the project Advancing Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) Development for NM Risk Assessment and Categorisation (the NanoAOP project), led by Vireo Advisors LLC and with participation from NanoCommons (represented by UoB) on the data management aspects, to assess

¹⁵ <https://www.vimmp.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://emmc.info/emmo-info/>

¹⁷ <https://emmc.info/moda/>

¹⁸ <https://www.oecd.org/science/nanosafety/45910212.pdf>

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the applicability of the principles established by the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics for establishment of AOPs for NMs. The scope of the project was to develop a methodology to identify, analyse and evaluate existing nanotoxicology literature with the objective to prioritize Key Events (KEs) relevant for NMs, and to demonstrate this approach to building NMs AOPs via a case study. Having reviewed the existing literature and databases (starting from the Swiss VRI database which was a hand-curated toxicology database of papers from 2007-2013) a case study focussing on 3 KEs related to the tissue inflammation pathway was selected, i.e., inflammation, oxidative stress and cytotoxicity, in order to analyse the empirical evidencebase to inform AOP development and assessment for NMs. Having selected the endpoints of interest, UoB undertook a major effort in mining and extracting the data from papers spanning the period 2013-2020 for seven NMs (Silver, Cerium Oxide, Copper Oxide, Multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes, Single-walled Carbon Nanotubes, Titanium Dioxide, Zinc Oxide) and established a modified database called the ‘Nano-AOP database’ which consists of data extracted from 119 publications from the original Swiss-VCI database and from 124 publications from the phase-2 literature review, leading to a grand total of 243 publications and 294 studies since some publications looked at more than one nanomaterial or test system. The NanoAOP database is aligned with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) guiding principles and will be accessible as part of the [NanoCommons KnowledgeBase](#)¹⁹. The methodology for developing KEs relevant for NMs from evidence gathered from the literature, and the strategy to prioritize identified potential KEs for future development as demonstrated by the tissue inflammation case study resulted in a publication (Halappanavar *et al.*, 2020) and three OECD reports, covering: (i) a systematic process for mining the nanotoxicity literature to identify potential KEs relevant for MNs (ENV/JM/MONO(2020)33), (ii) the case study on Tissue Injury (ENV/JM/MONO(2020)34), and (iii) the Workshop Report and Recommendations (ENV/JM/MONO(2020)35). A community statement and a roadmap for the further development of the AOP framework to decision making for NMs, based on the latter report, has been prepared and published with the participation of NanoCommons members (Ede *et al.*, 2020).

European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs (EPPN)

The [EPPN](#)²⁰ was formed to boost the European competitiveness through the exploitation of the existing European pilot line production facilities (across Europe) in the area of nanotechnology and advanced material technologies by creating a network of fully connected and collaborating pilot lines and boost the effectiveness and the efficiency of existing (and future) pilot line facilities and by creating a digital ecosystem acting as an interactive marketplace for professional members. Connecting NanoCommons to this network would bring together NM producers and risk assessors and could provide important stimuli to establish safety aspects as part of early product design and, in this way, to realise safety-by-design. To lay out the opportunities, the NanoCommons project was invited to participate in a EPPN

¹⁹ <https://ssl.biomax.de/nanocommons/>

²⁰ <https://www.eppnetwork.com/>

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workshop in November 2019. More details on the workshop are given in Deliverable D2.5 (2nd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop with TA calls and demonstrations) and below in the section on “Conference sessions and workshops for stakeholders”. NanoCommons distributed, on the ground and also via email after the event, its “Community needs” online survey, in order to understand the specific requirements of early stage safety testing and to be able to customise NanoCommons offerings to these needs. Unfortunately, the feedback was very low with only 5% of the workshop participants submitting answers to the survey. Nevertheless, NanoCommons has actively been interacting with the EPPN from then on to share its know-how and help the pilot projects addressing interesting topics for individual projects or collectively via the EPPN, as European Network of Pilot Production Facilities with SMEs, start-ups and large enterprises. Even with this intensive and continuous outreach, the interaction has not led to a successful TA application from the EPPN or one of its members. To understand the reasons why the NanoCommons services are not at a stage where they can be applied in pilot line facilities, NanoCommons is considering initiating an individual Case Study in collaboration with the EPPN and/or its potential successor, the [SusNanoFab project](#)²¹, to identify pain points in pilot line operation, which could be addressed by NanoCommons, and what gap prohibits the use in their current form. The objective of this case study will be a point of discussion in year 4 of the project (2021) and a decision will be made together with the other proposed case studies for the second set to be covered in Deliverable 9.4.

GO FAIR

The GO FAIR initiative aims to co-ordinate and disseminate the use of the FAIR data model to provide for the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of data resources and stakeholders across domains. Within the NanoCommons consortium, there is a strong commitment to the FAIR data concept, with many of the tools being built-up from inception as being FAIR-compliant (i.e., eNanoMapper). It is expected that by adhering to FAIR data principles, the NanoCommons infrastructure will be well-placed to offer services in data storage, retrieval and analysis that can serve the wider community, not just in the area of nanosafety data but data scientists in other, neighbouring fields as well fostering also the exchange between these fields. To that end, NanoCommons is determined to follow the latest efforts in the development of protocols and standards for FAIR data development. Partner UM is one of the leads of the GO FAIR Chemistry Implementation Network (Coles et al., 2020). With this in mind, and in collaboration with the Gov4Nano Consortium, several meetings were attended that were organised by GO FAIR to exchange newest developments, approaches and concepts and in this way guarantee a harmonised implementation of the FAIR principles. An initial meeting at the GFISCO office in Hamburg, provided the context and the background required to draft a manifesto outlining the basic principles governing the adoption of FAIR principles in the setting of nanosafety information, within the context of the human and environmental health and safety data related to Nano and Advanced Materials. A subsequent meeting

²¹<https://susnanofab.eu/>

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was organised by the GFISCO office (International FAIR convergence symposium: 27.11.2020-04.11.2020) whose theme was concentrated on the convergence of various Implementation Networks from a variety of domains. This initiative has the goal of coordinating the ontologies and semantics necessary for Implementation Networks to communicate across a wide variety of domains. Such a coordinated approach is especially important since the FAIR principles alone, especially with respect to metadata standards, are very general and have to be translated into more practical guidelines by the communities. An example for such practical work is adopting the concept of [FAIR Maturity Indicators²²](#) by NanoCommons, NanoSolveIT, RiskGONE, and Gov4Nano (Ammar et al., 2020), and developing those based on existing metadata standards like the Minimum Information Reporting in Bio-Nano Experimental Literature (MIRIBEL, Faria *et al.*, 2018) in an interoperable way to other communities represented in GO FAIR.

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

[EOSC²³](#) is the central initiative of the European Commission to develop a trusted, virtual, federated environment that cuts across borders and scientific disciplines to store, share, process and re-use research digital objects (like publications, data, and software) following FAIR principles. It is meant to be the envelope federating existing research data infrastructures in Europe. NanoCommons started very early with interacting with EOSC because of the clear push by the EC to connect and combine infrastructures across community boundaries but even more important because of the shared vision on open data and open science.

NanoCommons was participating together with the OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure project in the EOSC-hub Week, 10 – 12 Apr 2019 / Prague, and the “Building EOSC through the H2020 projects current status and future directions” workshop, 9 – 10 Sep 2019 / Brussels, where connections to projects like EOSC-hub and EOSC-Life and also other infrastructures like OpenAIRE and ENVRI. This was then followed up by inviting EOSC representatives to the OpenRiskNet final workshop, 23 – 24 Oct 2019 / Amsterdam. NanoCommons was introduced by Iseult Lynch as one of the beneficiaries and the successors of OpenRiskNet with respect to providing services to EOSC. This was followed by general introductions to EOSC, OpenAIRE, eInfraCentral and EOSC-hub with a final panel discussion on the lessons learned and next steps, funding opportunities and alignment with EOSC initiative, services marketplace and the EOSC early adopters calls. These interactions resulted in an application to the EOSC-hub early adopter programme to support moving the core infrastructure and NanoCommons services to EOSC computer resources and establish it as an EOSC service provider and community. This is now followed by becoming an associated partner in the new EGI-ACE project providing support and resources to NanoCommons for the next 2.5 years.

Being able to provide NanoCommons services as a part of EOSC will give an immense boost to the

²²https://github.com/ammar257ammar/NanoMaturityIndicators/blob/main/Gen2_MI_R1.3_NT_MIRIBEL.md

²³https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

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dissemination efforts. This has three aspects: 1) new users also from neighbouring communities will be reached, 2) service providers from the nanosafety community will see the benefits of promotion of their services to the EOSC communities by becoming part of NanoCommons, and 3) service providers from other communities already on EOSC will use the increased interoperability to build interfaces to NanoCommons and, in this way, enrich the functionality offered by NanoCommons.

InChI Trust

A simplified representation of a NM would be very valuable in many applications ranging from database searches, over input generation for nanoinformatics studies, to separating two nanoforms in regulatory applications. Similar representations for small molecules like SMILES and InChI have been applied very successfully but are not applicable in their current form. Therefore, a workshop was organised by NanoCommons and NanoSolveIT to establish requirements for such a NM representation and evaluate existing solutions if they could be extended to NMs. The choice was made in favour of InChI since the layered structure can encode different properties and can be easily extended as demonstrated by derived representations for mixtures, polymers and reactions. In follow-up activities led by representatives of the two projects but also including additional partners, a first version of an InChI for NMs or short NInChI was designed and published (Lynch et al, 2020). This publication and previous interactions with developers of the InChI standard resulted in the [InChI Trust](#)²⁴ becoming aware of this initiative. This organisation coordinates all activities around the InChI standard and develops and promotes the use of the IUPAC InChI open-source chemical structure representation algorithm. We were contacted at the end of December 2020 and invited to discuss the next steps in terms of moving our alpha version of the NInChI into an InChI Trust standard extension. A first scoping meeting was held on 11 Jan 2021, wherein it was agreed to establish an InChI Working Group on an InChI for NMs and the NanoCommons coordinator was appointed as the Chair of the working group. From the side of NanoCommons, the working group will be supported by a specific case study coordinating the internal development activities towards the standard version and support tools for the creation of NInChIs based on user input as well as the interactions with the partners from the InChI Trust bringing in additional expertise from work on the other InChI extensions.

The terms of reference for the InChI Working Group on an InChI for NMs include the following aspects:

- Is a NM an extension of a molecule, or is a molecule a component of a NM? If it is the former, then an AuxInfo approach might be best.
- Is the NM InChI canonical? The RInChI achieves this by minimising the information in the main string, and using AuxInfo to hold anything with a floating point number
- Can developments of the core InChI, including improved descriptions of organometallics and inorganics, fit easily into the Nano InChI without requiring substantial reprogramming?
- Does the Nano InChI describe NMs in a way which is globally accepted, or might take up in some regions be higher than in others?

²⁴ <https://www.inchi-trust.org/>

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- How should the Nano InChI software interact with the core InChI software? Would the aim be to integrate it, or could it be an independent program which called the core software whenever an InChI needed to be generated?

The goal is to achieve an InChI Trust standard for NMs by the end of the NanoCommons project or earlier, and to have demonstrated the utility of the NInChI through its implementation into the NanoCommons Knowledge Base and its utilisation in other projects such as NanoSolveIT.

The NanoSafety Cluster as stakeholder

While in the previous section, the NSC was introduced as a strategic collaborator to increase stakeholder access, here we will focus on the support NanoCommons gave to the NSC and its members and how they benefited from this support. In this way, the beneficiaries of the NanoCommons consultancy and training activities are illustrated, and the tangible outcomes that were generated during these conferences and discussions with groups of projects, in the form of TA applications and usage of TA services, are documented. In addition to the very specific support presented below, NanoCommons offered its expertise especially in harmonisation and interoperability for data but also nanoinformatics tools in all NSC working groups, either as leaders as presented above or as frequent attendees. These working groups as well as NanoCommons have the advantage that they are independent from specific research and innovation projects and, thus, knowledge can be shared at the same time with a larger, cross-project group helping to form a common understanding and strengthening of the community. All these interactions cannot be presented here. However, one example with tentative outcome is the work in WG C on Exposure and Hazard Assessment leading to a strong collaboration with the GRACIOUS project on exposure and release data templates, uploading and sharing and on terminology harmonisation supported by the GRACIOUS Ontology WIKI now being provided to all NSC projects.

Training

NanoCommons organised training activities during events of the NSC and, in this way, targeting this specific stakeholder group. The activities during the NanoSafety Cluster Week in Copenhagen have already been described in detail in Deliverable 2.5. This was followed-up by Martin Himly from PLUS partner organizing two educational full-day events as satellite workshops/webinars/hackathons to the NanoSafe Digital Conference. At these events, members of many currently ongoing projects of the nanosafety community and beyond were participating. The audience covered a multi-sectoral crowd of academics, regulators, industrial researchers, and also people interested in the socioeconomic effects of nanotechnology. The NanoCommons team was primarily involved in a educational/training sessions dedicated to nanosafety data management, metadata reporting style, scientific quality assurance, parameters/criteria for data FAIRness, human and environmental exposure/distribution modeling, workflows for automatic TEM image analysis and upload/download of NanoCommons

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Knowledge Base-annotated data for NMs, *etc.* More details are given below.

EU NanoSafety Cluster week in Copenhagen

Even if the EU NSC week was already reported in detail in Deliverable D2.5, we include it here again focusing on the impact the presentations had. Besides multiple oral presentations on the project and its results, NanoCommons was given the opportunity to present the TA offerings in a specific area at the poster session. Overall, six posters were presented grouped around the central poster [“Transnational Access @ NanoCommons”](#)²⁵ explaining the TA concept, what areas are covered and how to apply. This was then complemented by more specific posters like [“NanoCommons TA - UoB: Data management in nanosafety research. From bench to database thus streamlining analysis and publication”](#)²⁶ and [“NanoCommons - Opportunities for accessing nanoinformatics and predictive models for environmental fate”](#)²⁷. In the TA call opened shortly after the EU NSC week, 8 new applications were received and this high number can at least partly be attributed to the successful dissemination and initial discussions during the event like the one with the ASINA project leading directly to the TA project NC16.

European Risk Governance Council – Risk Governance of NMs: 3 European Projects Working Together: Gov4Nano & NANORIGO & RiskGONE

To boost the effect and synergies between the funded projects addressing governance and nanoinformatics, an interaction commitment between the projects Gov4Nano²⁸, NANORIGO²⁹ and RiskGONE³⁰ has been agreed. These three projects will develop a framework and a portal for the envisaged European Nano Risk Governance Council (NRGC), where tools and data management will play a key role. An inter-project core group on data management has been formed that will link the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure and potentially also other NanoCommons services with the NRGC portal and framework. NanoCommons is feeding directly into this core group (which is in fact Chaired by the NanoCommons coordinator, Iseult Lynch, on behalf of RiskGONE) and supports the development of the decision support tools for the NRGC and the integration of datasets and tools to facilitate risk assessment. NanoCommons will also foster the knowledge exchange between the projects by addressing harmonisation and interoperability issues in the area but also generally as part of its leadership role in the different NSC working groups as described above and especially in WG G

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/3693694#.YB0yAehKiUk>

²⁶ https://storage.googleapis.com/nanocommons/resources/2020/03/05/NanoCommons_-_UoB_TA_-_Copenhagen-IL.pdf

²⁷ https://storage.googleapis.com/nanocommons/resources/2020/02/28/Walker_et_al.pdf

²⁸ <https://www.gov4nano.eu/>

²⁹ <http://nanorigo.eu/>

³⁰ <https://riskgone.eu/>

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on Regulations & Risk Governance and WG F on Data Management.

A current activity of the core group is the development of a paper on best practices for data curation and assessment of data fitness for purpose for re-use. One of the case studies for this paper to be performed in collaboration with EUON is to develop criteria for data / information to be included on their website. The plan is to submit the joint paper mid-2021. Additionally, NanoCommons will support the 3 projects in the data collection and curation for their joint and individual case studies. For example, Gov4Nano are considering a case study on Electronic Laboratory Notebooks that will build on NanoCommons activities in this direction, as reported also in NanoCommons Deliverable D9.1.

Safe-by-design projects

Four projects, ASINA, SABYDOMA, SAbyNA and SbD4Nano, were funded under the H2020 NMBP-15-2019³¹ call. These were collectively approached by NanoCommons since harmonisation of approaches and sharing data across project boundaries would be highly beneficial for these related projects and can be facilitated by NanoCommons. Besides the individual, customised support offered to the projects described below, NanoCommons also offers its support for the harmonisation and interoperability across the projects in a similar way as described above for the governance projects. Again, the working NSC groups will play an important role here as an independent, cross-project discussion and guidance forum. Besides WG F, the strong involvement of NanoCommons in WG E on Innovation and Safer by Design even if not in a leading role is of major importance here.

SABYDOMA and SbD4Nano are planning to link their data to the NanoCommons Knowledge Base. The data of both projects will be included in eNanoMapper profiting from the already established connection between this data warehouse and the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure. The specifics for a TA have still to be defined but the collaboration and connection is already formally included in their Data Management Plans.

The plans on the collaboration with the SAbyNA project are much more evolved and a TA has been submitted (NC 21). SAbyNA is interested in an implementation and validation of the FAIR principle for their production and management of data. This will ensure that high quality data is flowing into the data repository, which was decided to be the NanoCommons Knowledge Warehouse.

Finally, the ASINA project has also already submitted a TA application (NC 16). During the writing of the proposal no dedicated data repository was specified and the TA is designed to provide the NanoCommons Knowledge Warehouse as the solution to be adopted.

³¹ NMBP-15 - Safe by design, from science to regulation: metrics and main sectors (RIA): https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_NMBP-15-2019

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Interactions with “Young Scientists” within and beyond the nanosafety field

Making especially young scientists aware of the importance of following high-quality standards during study design, study execution, data collection and execution is essential to achieve general adoption of such standards resulting in reproducible science and FAIR data. Therefore, NanoCommons put a strong focus on this stakeholder group. Two entire days of face-to-face training were pursued at the [1st International Young Scientist Forum \(IYSF\)](#)³², which was organized as a satellite symposium of the [12th International Particle Toxicology Conference \(IPTC\)](#)³³. Both events took place in Salzburg 9-13 September, 2019. Members of the PLUS, BfR, and UoB partners were active in the Scientific and Organizing Committees and therefore operational in shaping the programme to effectively disseminate NanoCommons’ intentions in regard to data FAIRness and promotion of TA services.

WP8 Key highlights & achievements - engaging early stage researchers

Interactive Session 1

Challenges in the field: What are the future research topics?

Nanotechnologies offer great potential of innovation in many different sectors. Investments in this area are very significant globally. Accordingly in the last decade our knowledge has increased significantly.

The aim of this session will be to discuss where to go in future. Possible questions to discuss together are:

- What are the emerging topics in our field?
- Have we adequately addressed all types of materials?
- What are new/ emerging materials?
- What about real exposures, co-exposure scenarios, mixtures?
- Why is it so difficult to translate scientific research findings into real applications?
- Why does it take so long to translate research findings into regulatory guidelines?
- ...and many more

Figure 2. Representative slide depicting the questions for the interactive brainstorming session on the future challenges of nanosciences which was conducted with the early-stage researchers at IYSF.

At IYSF, a keynote talk given by Iseult Lynch from UoB was paving the ground for an understanding of data FAIRness. Furthermore, an interactive session for the early-stage researchers on current challenges of the nanosafety field and a mixed team challenge on the same topic were conducted (see Figure 2 showing a slide with questions discussed in the session).

This allowed raising the attention of the future generation of scientists of different fields for available

³² <http://iptc2019.eu/IYSF2019.html>

³³ <http://iptc2019.eu/>

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and future (nano-)informatics tools provided via the NanoCommon Infrastructure. Additional questions were then answered at the presentation booth (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Presentation booth of the NanoCommons project advertising TA services run by the PLUS team during the poster session at the IPTC.

Conference sessions and workshops for stakeholders

NanoCommons partners participated and/or were involved in the organisation of a large number of conferences/workshops, in order to actively interact with the identified stakeholders and optimise our service offerings according to feedback on the fitness-for-purpose of the existing services and to develop new services in response to additional community needs collected at these conferences. In this section we highlight what was presented in each of the conferences and workshops and how, and which concrete stakeholders were reached. It will also be specifically stated if these conferences fostered follow-up activities and/or collaboration with neighbouring communities and/or with the strategic collaborators listed above.

European Researchers Night 2020

The PLUS team offered a contribution to the [European Researchers Night](https://researchersnight.eu/)³⁴ (ERN, 27 November 2020, 15:00 - 24:00h CET), an open public event this year transferred to the virtual format, and put the nanosafety-related theme into close relation with the currently omni-present topic, *i.e.*, the COVID-19 pandemic. In this regard, a highly interactive *Science Café* termed “Nano-Science & Health” was

³⁴ <https://researchersnight.eu/>

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offered. During an oral introductory presentation the basics of nano, the particularities for nanosafety assessment, aims of nanomedicine in general and the regulation of NMs and nanotechnology-enabled products were explained (see Figure 4). Further, the perspectives for the up-coming vaccination strategies combating COVID-19 were discussed. As the Science Cafe had a highly interactive character, an indeed very active audience was encountered at this virtual event. The introductory presentation was designed in close collaboration with the NMBP-13 projects, NANORIGO, Gov4Nano, and RISKGONE. All jointly established information materials are openly and freely available and have been deposited at the [NanoHUB](#)³⁵ of the EU NanoSafety Cluster.

Figure 4. One example slide representative for the topic of the *Science Cafe*, termed “Nano-Science & Health”, offered by the PLUS team at the Vienna event of the ERN (therefore, in German language). More details on the program can be viewed [here](#)³⁶.

EU Nanosafety Cluster Education Day & Training Day @ NanoSAFE 2020 Digital Conference

NanoCommons took the active role in facilitating educational presentations (at the NSC Education Day, 16 November 2020) and more in depth training sessions (at the NSC Training Day, 23 November

³⁵ <https://nanohub.org/groups/nanosafetycluster/collections/nmbp-13-education-resources--ern>

³⁶ <https://researchersnight.eu/2020/10/01/nano-science-gesundheit/>

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2020) from all NSC WGs. These two days, organized in collaboration with the [EU NSC Working Group \(WG\) A on Education, Training and Communication](#)³⁷, aimed to make more stakeholders aware of the work in the WGs and act as guidance for the entire NanoSafety community, including young researchers, and to highlight how individual research projects fit as puzzle pieces into the wider picture. In particular, the [Education Day \(16 Nov\)](#)³⁸ offered an orientation-giving event depicting the overall strategy behind NanoSafe(ty) (see Figure 5). At the [Training Day \(23 Nov\)](#)³⁹ more in depth training on e-tools, basic understanding of *in silico* models and insight into advanced cell culture models was provided in parallel session A. Moreover, detailed Q&A on analytical tools for NMs' characterization, an overview on the activities of WG G on risk governance and a stakeholder engagement workshop on science diplomacy were offered in parallel session B.

The following objectives were pursued to achieve this:

- to offer a **WG-overarching education/communication/discussion** event involving the audience *via* interactive sessions;
- to layout ways to **go beyond** with anything the nanosafety community has learned/developed to serve the emerging topics of Horizon Europe (emerging contaminants incl. microplastics, nanomedicine, safety assessment of novel/innovative/advanced materials for tomorrow along their entire life cycle);
- to foster participation in creating better sustainable materials (than *e.g.*, nanosilver in socks), technologies, medical approaches, *etc.*;
- to exhibit the perspectives of the NSC Working Groups and the different currently ongoing projects;
- to be **as interactive as possible** using **hands-on** activities, *e.g.*, by showing **how-to** operate e-tools, upload/retrieve data to/from repositories & perform models;
- to facilitate vivid contribution to discussions using survey tools such as Mentimeter, WooClap, VoxVote, *etc.*;
- to offer different perspectives in **pro/contra discussions**, *e.g.*, by defining **challenger - defender roles taken by experts on specific topics** or evtl. by dividing attendees into zoom breakout rooms;
- to show application of emerging NRG frameworks or SbD tools;
- to **request feedback** to user interfaces and enable stakeholder involvement.

³⁷<https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/working-groups/wga/>

³⁸<https://www.cea.fr/cea-tech/pns/nanosafe/en/Pages/Nanosafe-Conference/Nanosafe-2020/Program/Day-1.aspx>

³⁹<https://www.cea.fr/cea-tech/pns/nanosafe/en/Pages/Nanosafe-Conference/Nanosafe-2020/Program/Day-6.aspx>

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Welcome - NSC Education Day @ nanoSAFE'20

Block 1 - Emerging approaches in nanorisk assessment

- ▶ New developments in human hazard assessment - focus on AOP, QSAR, IATA
- ▶ Exposure & life cycle assessment - determination & modeling

Block 2 - Data workshop & e-tools for nano & beyond

- ▶ Data FAIRness, metadata completeness, scientific quality assurance
- ▶ Spectrum of e-tools along data life cycle

Block 3 - NanoRisk Governance & Safe-by-Design concepts - fit for translation to sustainable development?

- ▶ Features of nanoRGFs in development & current NRG concepts
- ▶ Elements of SbD for sustainable development & innovation

Martin Himly (PLUS)
Chair WG-A Education, Training, Communication
www.nanosafetycluster.eu

mailing list of WG-A Education, Training, Communication

Figure 5. Overview on the agenda of the EU NSC Education Day. More details on the program can be viewed [here](#), the program of the NSC Training Day can be found [here](#).

Overall, each day, more than 250 individual attendees were registered by the meeting platform, logging in from several European, Asian, American countries, and even Australia (see Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6. Country statistics of attendees.

As we learned from the global distribution of attendees, virtual education events seem to be more inclusive, less cost-prohibitive, and better in line with low carbon-emission policies than physical ones.

Figure 7. Global distribution of attendees.

2020 U.S.-EU NanoEHS COR Workshop: Bridging Insights and Perspectives

The U.S. National Nanotechnology Initiative (NNI) and the European Commission organized the ninth [annual meeting of the nanoEHS Communities of Research \(CORs\)](#)⁴⁰ as a virtual workshop (16-17 September 2020). This event was intended to align the activities between the U.S. and the EU and identify future needs and opportunities. Kicked-off by introductory presentation, the workshop fostered high-level discussions of nanoEHS and related areas to explore connections and synergies but also differences between the two continents. Because of its focus on data harmonisation and sharing, NanoCommons played a major role in the session on databases and informatics on the first day. Starting with the keynote lecture given by Thomas Exner from EwC, breakout sessions on the current state and the gaps seen slowing down the data sharing were led by Vladimir Lobaskin, UCD, as EU chair of the Characterization CoR and Fred Klaessig as the U.S. chair of the Databases and Computational Modeling for NanoEHS CoR. Like for the EU Nanosafety Cluster Education Day & Training Day described above, the virtual format resulted in a larger audience compared to previous meetings and active participation from both sides. However, discussions were limited to the outbreak sessions and not, as normal for face-to-face events, could not continue in the more informal setting of the social events around the meetings. To combine the advantages of face-to-face and virtual, a mixed system might be adopted with an annual face-to-face workshop and intermediate virtual meetings not only within individual CoRs but joined by all.

⁴⁰ <https://us-eu.org/2020-nanoehs-cor-workshop/>

1st Virtual Meeting with the Young NanoScientists

Due to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic early in 2020 and in order to reach a maximum audience worldwide, a number of virtual training events had been envisaged in the Plan for the 3rd year (see Deliverable D2.6). [The first of these events on 2 April 2020](#)⁴¹ (see Figure 8) was dedicated to the Young NanoScientists group, a regularly meeting group of scientists that had formerly been involved as PhD students in a number of nanosafety projects in H2020.

Figure 8. Intro slide depicting the NanoCommons team presenting the project intentions, TA services to the international Young NanoScientists group during a virtual event on 2 April 2020.

12th NanoTrust Conference

The [12th annual NanoTrust Conference](#)⁴² took place on 10 March 2020 in Vienna (Austria) organized by the NanoTrust project⁴³ of the Institute of Technology Assessment of the Austrian Academy of Sciences. At the conference, 30 experts from the German-speaking nano risk governance, academia, industry, SME and regulator communities discussed advanced materials in the light of safety and sustainability. The main focus was placed on exploring how the knowledge, approaches and resources

⁴¹ <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/events/29/1st-virtual-meeting-with-the-young-nano-scientist/>

⁴² <https://www.oeaw.ac.at/en/ita/events/current-events/11th-nanotrust-conference/>

⁴³ <https://www.oeaw.ac.at/en/ita/projects/current-projects/nanotrust/>

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built and nurtured throughout the past decade in the field of nanotechnology could be applied to the broader field of advanced materials.

NanoCommons had an active role in the conference with a presentation⁴⁴ (see Figure 9) about its role and impact. It aimed to interact with the audience regarding Advanced Materials, NanoGovernance, and NanoMedicine and illustrated the available "e-infrastructure" for nanosciences as well as for governance of safety aspects in the emerging area of advanced materials.

Figure 9. Intro slide from presentation advertising NanoCommons' activities and intentions.

Functional nanoporous carbonaceous materials workshop

LEITAT organised a workshop ([Renewable Energy Technology - POROUS4APP \(porous-4app.eu\)](http://www.porous-4app.eu)⁴⁵) as a satellite event of the [Future Materials Conference](https://materialsconference.yuktan.com/)⁴⁶. It brought together experts in the field of nanoporous carbonaceous materials going from the theoretical aspects up to the final applications including lab-scale and upscale demonstrations. Researchers from all over Europe presented recent advances in their field and were seeking for new partners for future collaborative projects. The

⁴⁴https://storage.googleapis.com/nanocommons/resources/2020/03/11/PresentationNC_NanoTrustTagung_Vienna_200310.pdf

⁴⁵<http://www.porous-4app.eu/workshops/>

⁴⁶<https://materialsconference.yuktan.com/>

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services offered by NanoCommons were disseminated in this workshop by a short oral communication and leaflets were distributed to the participants of the workshop and Conference. In this way, we were able to reach-out to a broad range of different stakeholders from the Materials community and make them aware of the infrastructure offered by NanoCommons and how they can apply for all the services provided. However, individual follow-up discussions with individual parties, which showed interest during the workshop, are now needed to develop TA projects addressing the identified needs. As described in the next section, general presentations and leaflets can only be the start to make stakeholders aware and interested, and continuous interactions are then needed giving support at every stage of a project or NM development process from the design phase to execution/production monitoring.

Follow-up activities to conference sessions and workshops for stakeholders

Finally, we will revisit here conferences and workshops reported already in Deliverable 2.5 (*2nd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop with TA calls and demonstrations*) to evaluate the impact of NanoCommons dissemination. These have led to long-term relationships with stakeholder groups, new collaborations and TA projects.

Boosting Innovation for EU Industry

Lee Walker (UKRI) presented the work of the project as an invited speaker at the Boosting Innovation Tour Conference held at BVV Trade Fairs, Brno, Czech Republic. The conference showcased several successful examples of innovation support with special emphasis on the Czech Republic, and was an opportunity to provide feedback to high level EU representatives and discuss the needs of the regional industry. The event was attended by over 100 delegates including representatives from research academic organisations, industrials (including many SMEs), and regional, national and international trade and research bodies.

The main objective of the conference was to present different EU national and regional initiatives to support innovation, access to research and technology infrastructure and financial support to boost innovation beyond 2020. As part of this programme, Lee Walker gave a short presentation highlighting the aims and approaches in promoting improved nanoinformatics through the provision of TA initiative.

As part of the event there was a matchmaking initiative in which discussions were held with companies and research institutes to explore the potential for development of TA applications. A productive discussion was held with Michal Urbánek, Nano Group Leader at the Central European Institute of Technology (CEITEC) which led to further discussions around holding a joint event to promote awareness of NanoCommons and encourage applications for TAs from users of the CEITEC facilities.

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This has been put on hold until COVID-19 travel restrictions are lifted.

The CEITEC Nano Research Infrastructure provides complex equipment, expertise and methods for nanotechnology and advanced materials R&D. The CEITEC Nano facilities for nanofabrication, nanocharacterization, structural analysis and X-ray tomography enable complete fabrication of nanostructures and nanodevices and their characterization down to the sub-nanometre level in an entirely clean environment. In our discussions it was apparent that provision of support in nanoinformatics would benefit users of the CEITEC Nano core facility. The next steps are to schedule and plan for a joint NanoCommons / CEITEC event in 2021.

EPPN Workshop: Pilot production lines for the health, transport, and industry

The NanoCommons project was invited to participate in the workshop organised by the [EPPN](#)⁴⁷ (European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs) on 5 November 2019 in San Sebastian (Spain). The workshop was an excellent opportunity for NanoCommons to present its benefits and offerings for the pilot lines, aligned with the TAs.

The project was presented as an initiative **supporting the pilots and the OITBs** as it provides access to state-of-the-art expertise (in **nanoinformatics and data management tools, modelling and risk assessment services**) free of charge (by means of TA activities). The goal was to raise awareness among EPPN partners and facilitate them to take advantage of the NanoCommons services, facilities and knowledge to advance their work, solve problems and take their research to the next level. Unfortunately, this did not result in the uptake of NanoCommons services by EPPN as already mentioned above in the section on EPPN as a possible strategic collaborator.

OpenRiskNet Final Workshop

As already mentioned above, NanoCommons took part in the OpenRiskNet final workshop, 23 – 24 Oct 2019 / Amsterdam, as presenter (“Adoption of OpenRisknet solutions by NanoSafety community and NanoCommons infrastructure” by Iseult Lynch) and as participant in the final panel discussion. On the one side, this was a good opportunity to present NanoCommons to the broader toxicity and risk assessment community represented by more than 50 participants and show the mutual benefits of collaboration. On the other hand, the participation of representatives of different EOSC projects showed the early success in establishing (nano)safety as part of the EOSC universe. Additionally, it allowed for planning of specific next steps to strengthen and sustain its position therein now realised in the partnership in the EGI-ACE project resulting in a larger visibility of NanoCommons outside of its own community.

⁴⁷ <https://www.eppnetwork.com/>

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Science is Wonderful

On 24-26 September 2019, NanoCommons participated in the exhibition EU Research & Innovations Days - “Science is Wonderful”, in Brussels (Belgium).

NanoCommons brought closer to the general public (schools, families and young people) its actions and the benefits of nanotechnology on everyday life, interacting with the public through hands-on experiments, live demonstrations and face-to-face chats with researchers and showing how science impacts our daily lives.

During the event, the NanoCommons representatives Cristiana Gheorghe and Anastasios Papadiamantis (UoB), supported by NovaMechanics’ Antreas Afantitis and Georgia Melagraki interacted with members of the public, mainly school children, and informed them on the benefits of nanotechnology and how we can copy and exploit natural occurring nanostructures in everyday life. The NanoCommons representatives discussed the implications from the use of NMs in everyday life and how the EC, through Horizon Europe, wants to focus on EU citizens and economies’ needs, as addressed by major EU and national MS policy goals. In this sense, the research infrastructures part of Horizon Europe aligns with the UN’s globally agreed Sustainable Development Goals as well.

More details about this event can be found in the deliverable D2.5 - 2nd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop with TA calls and demonstrations.

Conclusions

This report presents the NanoCommons activities to organise the interactions with its key stakeholders. While the first reporting period was focused on establishing the NanoCommons Infrastructure, including the concepts for data management and nanoinformatics services and the first versions of guidance and training materials in these areas, the second reporting period involved intense dissemination of these offers to achieve high uptake, mainly via TA projects as well as promoting self-service use of the approaches were feasible. However, due to the COVID-19 outbreak, these dissemination activities were not possible in the way anticipated in the Description of Action as a set of workshops with different stakeholders. Instead, many other channels were used to reach the largest number of stakeholders possible. This included strong representation of NanoCommons in face-to-face conferences and workshops, as long as this was possible, and then in webinars, online training and hackathons, and online conferences. The sections **Conference sessions and workshops for stakeholders** and **Follow-up activities to conference sessions and workshops for stakeholders** not only list these participations and presentations, but concentrate on the stakeholders reached and the tangible outcomes from them, such as specific TA applications and expansion of our potential user community into neighbouring research communities. Additionally, some completely new ways to address stakeholders were pursued. Strategic collaborators (see section **Interactions with strategic**

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collaborators to increase stakeholder access) were identified to increase the benefits available to NanoCommons users by mutual exchange of expertise and harmonisation of services, but also to penetrate the neighbouring communities (e.g., toxicology in its broadest sense, materials manufacturing and virtual materials marketplace), and thereby extend the stakeholder base. Finally, the support given to the EU NanoSafety Cluster as one of the major stakeholders was evaluated in the section **The NanoSafety Cluster as stakeholder** with respect to the role NanoCommons is playing in:

- 1) bringing together projects with similar objects or even funded under the same call already at a very early stage and how this can be extended to new funded project clusters and
- 2) training individuals and especially young researchers as well as complete projects in areas like data management and nanoinformatics.

Abbreviations

AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathway

COR – Communities of Research

EMMC – European Materials Modelling Council

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud

EPPN - European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs

EUON - European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials

InChI - International Chemical Identifier

IPTC - International Particle Toxicology Conference

IYSF - International Young Scientist Forum

KB - Knowledge Base

KEs - Key Events

KI - Knowledge Infrastructure

NInChI – proposed extension of the InChI for NMs

NMs - nanomaterials

NRGC - Nano Risk Governance Council

OECD - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

RinChI – extension of the InChI for chemical reactions

TA - Transnational Access

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